

Title:

Advancing Climate Resilience Capacity of the Sankofa Wetland Park, the Lower Ninth Ward, and Surrounding Communities (Sankofa-ARC)

The Lower 9th Ward of New Orleans, home to the Sankofa Wetland Park, is one of the city's lowest-lying areas, with elevations ranging from near sea level to seven feet below. This area suffered catastrophic flooding over 10 feet deep during Hurricane Katrina in 2005, leading to significant loss of life and property damage. The remarkable community resilience is showcased with projects like the Sankofa Wetland Park that transformed from a debris-filled wasteland into a vibrant habitat for diverse wildlife and a model of sustainable green infrastructure, playing a crucial role in stormwater management. Positioned at -7 feet below sea level, it significantly mitigates flood risks by temporarily storing stormwater, especially during severe weather events, with its design helping to slow and manage water flow.

The Advancing Climate Resilience Capacity of the Sankofa Wetland Park, the Lower Ninth Ward, and Surrounding Communities (Sankofa-ARC) project unites community leaders, park caretakers, and local environmental consulting expertise with academic support to enhance green infrastructure and advance climate justice in Orleans and Saint Bernard Parish, Louisiana. This initiative leverages the wholistic health, justice, and community-strengthening expertise of the Sankofa Community Development Corporation (Sankofa-CDC) alongside Tulane University's experience with NASA-sponsored open science for environmental and climate justice applications. A flagship project of Sankofa-CDC, the 40-acre Wetland Park, serves as a vital green space designed to boost urban resilience by absorbing stormwater, promoting environmental education, and fostering community ties through interaction with natural ecosystems.

The upcoming Sankofa-ARC activities will build on existing efforts at the Wetland Park, which include monthly water quality monitoring, avian surveys, quarterly impact reporting, and contributions to an Army Corps of Engineers Storm Water Management Modeling (SWMM) project, due for completion in mid-2024. Utilizing NASA Earth Observation data streams LS, MODIS/VIIIRS, including new observations from the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission, this project will enhance existing, but limited, hydraulic models into a comprehensive eco-hydrological model for monitoring and climate scenario forecasting. This will be achieved by integrating spatial-temporal land cover mapping, in-situ measurements, and climate forcing inputs into a landscape-scale Soil and Water Integrated Model (SWIM), providing a critical advancement in evidence for community climate resilience decision-making. Co-authored and co-designed with Sankofa leadership, technical staff, the Sankofa Community Action Advisory Board (CAAB), and a team from Tulane University, the Sankofa-ARC embodies a collaborative frontier where advanced science meets grassroots community action, culminating in a robust climate resilience solution for sustainable development, environmental justice, and resilient futures.

The project has three objectives supported by detailed tasks and clear roles and responsibilities:

1. Co-lead a Community Climate Risk and Resilience Assessment (CCRA) by inclusive engagement of Sankofa stakeholders in participatory mapping to assess both risks and capacities to manage these risks in the Wetland Park and surrounding communities within Y1.
2. Co-design and co-implementation of community climate resilience solution that enhances understanding of the capacities of the Wetland Park and green infrastructure, changes across the catchment area, and potential climate-

related impacts on the Wetland Park and surrounding communities with at least three eco-hydrological model result visualizations and one map by the end Y2.

3. Critical reflective developmental evaluation and dedicated capacity development is integrated into all project activities with at least one final reflective evaluation convening and three dedicated capacity development events in Y3